

Mass Spectral Fragmentation of Some Acid Terephthalic Esters

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Mass spectral fragmentation of acid terephthalic esters of 1-phenylethanol and its *para*-ethyl derivative have been recorded. The pattern of fragmentation of the esters are discussed in the light of their temperature controlled pyrolysis.

THE results obtained from the thermal decomposition studies of the acid terephthalic esters of 1-phenylethanol and some of its *para* substituted derivatives prompted the present investigation. Pyrolysis of the esters under isothermal and non-isothermal conditions by thermogravimetric methods gave interesting results¹. Terephthalic acid and the corresponding styrenes were obtained during the thermal degradation and the mechanism was interpreted as one comparable to that of the McLafferty rearrangement of similar esters occurring in mass spectral fragmentation. In the light of these results mass spectra of 1-phenylethyl hydrogen terephthalate (I) and 1-(*p*-ethyl phenyl)ethyl hydrogen terephthalate (II) were recorded and the fragmentation pattern is discussed.

was obtained at m/z 270 and that for compound II at m/z 298 with high relative abundance. In either case ion peak at m/z 149 was found with very high relative abundance. This indicates fragmentation

TABLE I—SIGNIFICANT FRAGMENTS AND THEIR RELATIVE ABUNDANCE

Compound I		Compound II	
m/z	Relative abundance (%)	m/z	Relative abundance (%)
77	69.0	105	>10
104	84.0	117	87
105	81.0	132	100
120	68.6	133	72
149	100.0	149	97
166	<10.0	166	<10
270	73.0	298	92

Experimental

Very pure samples of 1-phenylethyl hydrogen terephthalate and 1-(*p*-ethyl phenyl)ethyl hydrogen terephthalate were prepared by known methods². Mass spectra were obtained using Varian MAT CH7 mass spectrometer. The filament current and potential were 100 μ A and 70 eV, respectively. The significant portion of the spectra relevant to the present study were obtained also at higher sensitivity.

Results and Discussion

The relative abundance of the fragments significant to the present investigation are given in Table 1. The molecular ion peak of compound I

which is characteristic of esters of phthalic acid and terephthalic acid and can be attributed to the ion IV^{3,4}. The relatively large abundance of the fragments with m/z 104 from I and that with m/z 132 from II indicates formation of the corresponding styrene molecular ions III. This stage of the fragmentation may be depicted as shown below.

Molecular ion peak at m/z 166 supports this mode of fragmentation. It may be mentioned that evidence of metastable ion peaks supporting the mode of fragmentation are very few. However, in the

case of 1-(*p*-ethyl phenyl)ethyl hydrogen terephthalate a metastable ion peak was observed at m/z 103.5. This is in excellent conformity with the fragmentation of the substrate giving rise to the styrene molecular ion (m/z 132) which subsequently eliminates $\text{CH}_3\cdot$ radical from the *p*-ethyl substituent giving rise to the ion peak with m/z 117.

The fragments with m/z 105 and 133 from compounds I and II, respectively represent the corresponding phenyl methyl carbonium ion V arising out of the cleavage of the alkyl oxygen bond of the ester group. Elimination of a $\text{CH}_3\cdot$ radical is quite

(R = H or C_6H_5)

possible from the carbonium ion V formed from II. The high relative abundance (87%) of the ion peak at m/z 117 from compound II can also be due to this.

The fragmentation patterns of the two esters have certain similarities under electron impact and thermal conditions. Terephthalic acid and the corresponding styrenes were the products in the temperature controlled pyrolysis, through the possible formation of a cyclic transition state¹. In mass spectral study, ionic species derivable from terephthalic acid and the corresponding styrenes are found in relatively large abundance.

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